

Kaniadakis Distribution and Special Relativity

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In (1), it is argued that the Kaniadakis $\exp_k(x) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \}^{\text{power } 1/k}$ is linked to special relativistic variables. In (2), we argued that one may consider $\exp_k(x)$ with $x=-e_i/T$ arising from the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit yielding the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution with $\exp(x)=1+x+xx/2$ being a better approximation than $1+x$. Here we try to show that this argument also holds in both the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases, as does the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, suggesting that this alternative way of looking at the Kaniadakis distribution does not require any knowledge of special relativity.

Minimal Information Based on Constraints

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution

$$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

is the distribution based on the minimal amount of information contained in the constraints:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((2))$$

Thus, if $G = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ such that $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, then:

$$dG=0 = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } c_i d(\text{constraint } i) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Then: } h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ forces } p(e_i) dh/dp(e_i) = 1 \text{ or } h = \ln(p) \quad ((4))$$

Out of all of the $\{ p(e_i) \}$ solutions which satisfy the constraints ((2)), the MB distribution is the one representing the minimal information. Given that the Kaniadakis distribution $\exp_k(x)$ uses the same constraints ((2)), it cannot represent the minimal information distribution based on the two constraints ((2)) alone.

As a result, some other features must be present. In (1), it is argued that the $\exp_k(x)$ form:

$$\exp_k(x) = \{ \sqrt{1+kx} + kx \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \text{ with } x = -e_i/T \quad ((5))$$

is linked to special relativity. In (2), we argued that an alternative way of creating $\exp_k(x)$ was to consider a distribution based on a power law such that for $e_i/T \ll 1$ one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. We first revisit this argument and try to show that it holds in the relativistic and nonrelativistic case, in order to argue that one may obtain $\exp_k(x)$ using this idea in either the nonrelativistic or relativistic situations.

Nonrelativistic Case

In the nonrelativistic case: $e_i = .5m v_i^2$ where v_i is 1-D speed. ((6))

Thus, one is guaranteed that for v_i very small, one may have $e_i/T \ll 1$. If one wishes to have a polynomial in $x = e_i/T$ to a power $1/k$, then this polynomial should approximate:

$$\exp(kx) \text{ for } x \ll 1 \quad ((7))$$

The simplest approximation is $1-x$, but $1-x+.5kx^2$ is a better one and we argued that the Kaniadakis distribution is based on the latter.

In such a case, one has ((5)) as the function which for $x \ll 1$ yields:

$$\exp(kx) \text{ approx} = 1 + kx + .5k^2x^2 \quad ((8))$$

As a result, this argument holds in the nonrelativistic case.

Relativistic Case

Here we consider the relativistic case for which: $e_i = \sqrt{m_0^2c^4 + p^2c^2}$. Unlike the nonrelativistic case, e_i cannot tend to 0, but we argue that one may still have:

$$e_i/T \ll 1 \quad ((9))$$

We consider two cases, a general e_i and $e_i = m_0c^2 + KE$ where $KE = .5mv^2$, i.e the nonrelativistic case. Then, in the limit of ((9)) one essentially has the nonrelativistic scenario:

$$\sqrt{1+kx} + kx \text{ approx} = 1 + .5kx + kx \quad ((10))$$

((10)) holds for an arbitrary e_i as long as ((9)) holds as well as for $e_i = m_0c^2 + KE$.

((10)) is a better approximation again for $\exp(kx)$ than $1-kx$.

Now imagine that one had a linear term and did not know the form: $\sqrt{1+kx}$, but wanted a second order approximation to $\exp(kx)$. Given kx , one would need:

$$f(kx) = 1 + .5kx \text{ for } x \ll 1 \quad ((11))$$

On the other hand, for $x \gg 1$, one must have $f(kx) = \text{constant} * kx$ ((12))

(as one wishes to have a power law drop-off).

$\sqrt{1+kx}$ is certainly a solution to ((11)) and ((12)).

Thus, we argue that the low $ei/T \ll 1$ limit applies to the Kaniadakis $\exp_k(x)$ becoming the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases.

Why Should $ei/T \ll 1$ Retrieve the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution?

We argued in the first paragraph that the MB distribution is the minimal information one. It leads to $\exp(-ei/T)$. In other words, there is no k power law parameter. If one considers a power law distribution a priori, then this seems to represent extra information from the minimal constraints ((2)). If, however, one is able to remove the effects of the power law, the one might have a minimal information distribution based on ((2)). Setting $k \rightarrow 0$ is one way to do this, but it seems that $ei/T \ll 1$ is another. In other words, for $ei/T \ll 1$, the effects of the power law disappear as it really applies to large ei/T . If there is no other information present in the $ei/T \ll 1$ limit, one would then expect the MB distribution to arise.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) argues that $\sqrt{1+kx} + kx$ is a variable linked with special relativity. In an earlier note (2), we argued that one may obtain the Kaniadakis distribution by seeking one which yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann for $ei/T \ll 1$ and becomes proportional to ei/T for $ei/T \gg 1$. We show that this idea holds whether one considers the problem from a nonrelativistic or relativistic point of view as does the MB form $C \exp(-ei/T)$. In one case, ei is nonrelativistic and in the other, relativistic. Low ei/T seems to be entirely a statistical situation.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Physical Origin of the power-tailed statistical distributions (2012)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1206.2250>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Kaniadakis Distribution and $ei/T \ll 1$ Considerations (preprint, zenodo, 2025)